

Tropical Humid Heat Stress Crosses a Critical Threshold in a Warming World

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Key Points:

- Global potential productivity loss from humid heat stress has risen rapidly since the mid-1980s, crossing a critical threshold.
- Potential productivity loss in the Asian monsoon region rises nonlinearly with increasing moisture, warm pool SST, and population.
- Humid heat stress-driven productivity loss shows strong ENSO link, allowing 1–6 month lead prediction for planning and mitigation.

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Abstract

Anthropogenic activities are pushing key Earth system components beyond safe thresholds, disrupting economies, ecosystems, and societies. Yet, climate action remains largely rhetorical, and sustainable development has stalled. Here, we show an abrupt increase in global potential productivity loss from humid heat stress (Humidex $> 45^{\circ}\text{C}$, WBGT $> 33^{\circ}\text{C}$) since the mid-1980s, with India contributing over half of the total increase. This coincides with Indo-Pacific sea surface temperatures exceeding 28°C and rapid population growth. The loss has continued and recently crossed a critical transition, suggesting a shift to a new state. On interannual timescales, strong correlation with ENSO indicates that such losses are predictable up to six months in advance, offering a window for adaptive planning. These findings reveal that accounting for humid heat stress significantly raises the estimated socioeconomic costs of climate change and highlights a feedback loop where climate impacts undermine the development pathways that contribute to those very impacts.

Plain Language Summary

Human activities are pushing the Earth's natural systems beyond safe limits, leading to severe disruptions in economies, ecosystems, and societies. Despite growing concerns, meaningful climate action remains limited. Our study shows that global potential productivity loss due to extreme humid heat stress (Humidex $> 45^{\circ}\text{C}$, WBGT $> 33^{\circ}\text{C}$) has increased abruptly since the mid-1980s, with India alone contributing more than half of this rise. We also identify that humid heat stress has crossed a critical threshold in the Asian monsoon, where rising moisture levels in association with record-high warm pool sea surface temperatures ($> 28^{\circ}\text{C}$) and rapid population growth, creating significant socioeconomic risks. Additionally, we find that humid heat stress and productivity loss are closely linked to El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO), allowing for predictions up to six months in advance. Our findings suggest that climate change impacts may be much more costly than previously estimated when extreme heat is considered, highlighting a self-reinforcing cycle, where climate disruptions hinder the very development processes contributing to them.

1 Introduction

In the backdrop of a warming planet, the increasing frequency and intensity of extreme rainfall events (Goswami et al., 2006; Rajeevan et al., 2008; Roxy et al., 2017; Fu et al., 2010; Mason et al., 1999), extreme humid heat stress events (Freychet et al., 2022; Jeong et al., 2023) are disproportionately affecting the populated tropical countries (Im et al., 2017; Kjellström et al., 2018; Rogers et al., 2021). With warmer mean temperature and associated moisture content, the wet bulb temperature (WBT) in many tropical stations is already reaching 35°C and challenging human survivability (Raymond et al., 2020). Even when WBT does not exceed critical thresholds over large areas, the increasing duration of humid heat stress exposure measured, for example, by wet-bulb globe temperature (WBGT), is occurring on a broad scale and may lead to significant productivity loss (Morrissey et al., 2021; Parsons et al., 2022; Hajizadeh et al., 2014; Zander et al., 2015). It is estimated that the socio-economic loss due to weather extremes including both rainfall and heat extremes and their variability from a 3°C increase in global mean temperature would be as large as 10% of GDP for countries like India with much larger loss for sub-Saharan countries (Kotz et al., 2024; Waidelich et al., 2024). To minimize loss from the looming heat stress disasters, communication of the risk is critical (Cvijanovic et al., 2023) for disaster management and for adaptation policy. Yet, major tropical countries like India is still communicating the risk in terms of dry bulb temperature or heat stress index that is ineffective in communicating the risk. The situation is not different in other tropical countries. The lack of communication of the grav-

ity of the situation seems to be responsible for the lack of adaptive policy development and clear protocols for working under such conditions appropriate to individual countries, thereby increasing the health cost.

The impacts on health and productivity are due to both increases in temperature with global warming as well as changes in humidity which is at least partly attributable to changes in free-tropospheric moist static energy and convective quasi-equilibrium that prevails across tropical regions (Buzan & Huber, 2020; Byrne, 2021; Byrne & O’Gorman, 2016; Lutsko, 2021; Zhang et al., 2021; Zhang & Fueglistaler, 2020). Despite increasing recognition of the role of humidity in determining the magnitude of heat stress and nearly every heat stress index accounts for humidity (Ioannou et al., 2022), only a few epidemiological studies in South Asia take humidity into account (Dimitrova et al., 2021), and the operational definition of heatwaves, as well as heat action plans, are based on temperature alone (Kotharkar & Ghosh, 2022; Srivastava et al., 2022; Valiathan Pillai & Dalal, 2023). Similarly, most studies of heat stress over South Asia focus on the pre-monsoon season, even though high heat stress extends into the monsoon season (Justine et al., 2023; Koteswara Rao et al., 2020; Pai et al., 2013; Ratnam et al., 2016; Rogers et al., 2021). We note that this dichotomy is not unique to South Asia, indeed, the role of humidity in health outcomes is being debated in the health community across the world (Baldwin et al., 2023).

WBGT and advanced indices like the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) are widely used to assess heat stress by integrating multiple meteorological parameters, providing thresholds for occupational safety and activity planning (Havenith & Fiala, 2016; Kong & Huber, 2022). However, WBGT, expressed in °C and with values lower than actual temperatures, may understate perceived risk. An index that is simpler to compute, easier to communicate, and effective in humid tropical regions is thus desirable. We use Humidex (Masterton & Richardson, 1979; Diaconescu et al., 2023; Jeong et al., 2023) alongside WBGT to quantify changes in potential productivity loss, as it captures temperature–humidity effects, aligns qualitatively with human thermophysiological responses (Simpson et al., 2023), and can be derived from standard meteorological data. Humidex is also applied in labor productivity studies under humid heat stress (Foster et al., 2021).

To highlight the severity of humid heat stress increase in the tropics, the present study shows that the change in ‘potential’ productivity loss due to heat stress around 1980’s is abrupt and potentially crossed a critical point. In addition to providing a non-parametric statistical argument as to why this event should be termed a critical transition, we also provide a physical basis of why humid heat stress exposure should abruptly increase after the 1980s, as well as its predictability on year-to-year variability. Section 2 describes data used and methodology. Results are shown in Section 3 and summarized the study in section 4.

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Humidex and WBGT

Increasing air temperature combined with higher humidity can lead to increased perceived heat stress, creating a more uncomfortable and potentially dangerous environment due to the decreased cooling efficiency of the human body. The Humidex, which is introduced by Masterton and Richardson (1979), is an empirical heat stress index that relates to outdoor thermal discomfort experienced by the general population. The hourly 2m air temperature (T_a in °C) and dew point temperature (T_d in °K) from European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalysis version 5 (ERA5; Hersbach et al., 2020) for 1940-2020 with $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ horizontal resolution is used to calculate hourly Humidex. The Humidex index is calculated with the following equations:

$$\text{Humidex} = T_a + 5/9(e - 10) \quad (1)$$

$$e = 6.11 \times \exp(5416.883 \times (\frac{1}{273.15} - \frac{1}{T_d})) \quad (2)$$

where e is the vapour pressure. ERA5 does not provide hourly relative humidity (RH) data. Therefore, RH is estimated using T_a and T_d with the approximation of the Clausius-Clapeyron equation (Shaman & Kohn, 2009), using the following equations:

$$e_s = 6.11 \times \exp(5416.883 \times (\frac{1}{273.15} - \frac{1}{T_a})) \quad (3)$$

$$RH = 100 \times (e/e_s) \quad (4)$$

where e_s is the saturation vapour pressure. Saturation vapor pressure increases exponentially with temperature as per the Clausius-Clapeyron relation, leading to greater moisture sensitivity in warmer regions. As a result, tropical warming yields a much larger absolute increase in vapor pressure—for instance, a 1°C rise at 30°C increases saturation vapor pressure about three times more than the same rise at 10°C (e.g., in the high latitude region). As the moisture level increases in the atmosphere, the dew point temperature (the temperature at which the atmosphere is saturated with moisture) increases, leading to an increase in vapour pressure (equation 2). Humidex describes the level of outdoor thermal discomfort with the increase in the humidity level in the atmosphere (Masterton & Richardson, 1979; Jeong et al., 2023).

Wet-bulb globe temperature (WBGT) is calculated based on Kong and Huber (2022). The Python code is used from GitHub (<https://github.com/QINQINKONG/PyWBGT#citation>). WBGT is also used to measure heat stress in direct sunlight, which considers temperature, humidity, wind speed, sun angle, solar and long wave radiation. It is commonly used in sports, occupational health, and military settings to assess heat risk and guide safety measures during physical activities in hot and humid environments. Hourly 2m air temperature, dew point temperature, surface winds (10m), surface pressure, net surface and downward short wave, and long wave radiation from ERA5 are used to calculate WBGT.

2.2 Potential Occupational Productivity Loss (POPL)

In this study, we focus on estimating potential heat exposure, which represents the maximum possible level of exposure assuming no adaptive or protective measures are in place. This approach is intentional, as it isolates the contribution of purely meteorological factors, such as temperature and humidity, to extreme heat stress. By doing so, it allows us to assess the upper bound of exposure driven solely by climate variability, independent of socio-economic or behavioral adaptations. Moreover, assuming limited interannual variability in population enables a cleaner interpretation of the meteorological predictability associated with potential heat extremes. Hence, this framework provides a valuable baseline for understanding the physical limits of heat stress exposure, against which the effectiveness of future adaptation and mitigation strategies can be evaluated.

To estimate potential exposure of heat stress to the total working population (25-60 years), annual population numbers from hybrid gridded demographic data (Chambers, 2020) with $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ for 1950-2020 is used. This data contains age-wise number of population (0 to 65 years with intervals of 5 years, i.e. 0, 5, 10, ..., 65). In addition to this, gridded demographic data of total, urban and rural (1950-2020) is also used (*ISIMIP3a population input data*, 2024) to quantify POPL exposure levels in the rural and urban areas. The high-resolution ERA5 data is projected/regressed into the population data

156 grid before the calculation of humidex. WBGT and Humidex are calculated in every hour
 157 at each grid point globally for every 5% interval of relative humidity (i.e. 20 categories;
 158 0-5%, 5-10%, 10-15%, 15-20%, ..., 95-100%) during 7AM to 7PM local standard time.
 159 The hourly WBGT/humidex for a certain threshold and for each category is aggregated
 160 over a year. Humidex $> 45^{\circ}\text{C}$, is termed as serious danger and advised to suspend phys-
 161 ical activities (d&Ambrosio Alfano et al., 2011). Humidex is also used in humid trop-
 162 ical regions along with Wet-Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT; Cvijanovic et al., 2023),
 163 where it is shown that the threshold varies but structures in Humidex and WBGT is quite
 164 similar. Moreover, WBGT and Humidex indices are found to have a better association
 165 with human physiological parameters over Mediterranean and Middle-east regions (Boukan,
 166 West Azerbaijan and Iran; Zamanian et al., 2017). The WBGT threshold for extreme
 167 (or leve3) varies from 28°C to 35°C (Table S2 Schwingshackl et al. (2021)), while Brimicombe
 168 et al. (2023) used 33°C . The threshold values of WBGT for a very high risk of heat-related
 169 illnesses, as recommended by various international organizations, range between 28°C
 170 and 35°C (Cheung et al., 2016; Schwingshackl et al., 2021; Brimicombe et al., 2023). The
 171 calculated humidex/WBGT hour of a year is multiplied by the population of a grid point
 172 to estimate Potential Occupational Productivity Loss (i.e. POPL) in a year. It is im-
 173 portant to note that POPL reflects the potential productivity loss rather than the ac-
 174 tual loss. Estimating the actual loss is complex, as it depends on multiple factors includ-
 175 ing socioeconomic conditions, adaptive planning, infrastructure, public awareness, lifestyle
 176 etc.

177 The global POPL normalized by population (Humidex $> 45^{\circ}\text{C}$ in hours) as a func-
 178 tion of RH clearly divides it into humid and dry regimes (Figure S1) *i.e.* $(p_1 h_1 + p_2 h_2 +$
 179 $\dots + p_n h_n) / (p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_n)$, where p_i, h_i are population and Humidex hours, re-
 180 spectively at a land grid box i . The normalized POPL clearly show an intense exposur
 181 level in the dry RH zone for urban areas compared to rural areas (Figure S1 b,c). The
 182 dry regime lies within 0-25% of RH with maxima at around 10% RH (primarily in the
 183 arid and desert regions). This regime basically represents the Middle East and desert
 184 regions of South Asia and North Africa. Another maximum of normalized POPL lies around
 185 70% RH, which primarily represents the humid tropical countries. On the other hand,
 186 POPL based on WBGT shows intense heat exposure above 50% of RH. However, in the
 187 recent decades, POPL has also increased in the lower humidity range (i.e. 10-50% RH).
 188 Nevertheless, total POPL with 0-25% ($>25\%$) RH is considered dry (humid) POPL or
 189 dPOPL (hPOPL).

190 In the case of historical simulations or climate projections by IPCC CMIP6 mod-
 191 els, hourly calculation of Humidex is not possible, as outputs from climate models are
 192 frequently only available on a daily time step. Moreover, CMIP6 models usually do not
 193 archive vapour pressure and dew point temperature but provide relative humidity and
 194 daily maximum temperature (T_{max}). Therefore, approximations are used to calculate
 195 e using RH and T_{max} (Jeong et al., 2023; Diaconescu et al., 2023).

$$e = 6.112 \times 10^{7.5 \times T_{max} / (237.7 + T_{max})} \times RH / 100 \quad (5)$$

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$$Humidex = T_{max} + 5/9(e - 10) \quad (6)$$

197 Daily maximum temperature generally coincides with minimum relative humidity,
 198 with extreme heat occurring near the temperature peak (Diaconescu et al., 2023). As
 199 few CMIP6 models provide daily minimum RH, we compute daily Humidex from daily
 200 RH and T_{max} for Historical and piControl simulations (1950–2014) from nine models (Ta-
 201 ble TS1). This may overestimate Humidex, but since our focus is on changes due to his-
 202 torical anthropogenic warming (Historical–piControl), systematic biases from using daily
 203 mean RH are partly offset.

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2.3 Global predictors and HOPL anomalies

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The depth of the 20°C isotherm (D20) represents upper ocean heat content, a key source of heat and moisture for atmospheric convection (e.g., tropical cyclones, monsoons). During El Niño (La Niña), D20 deepens (shoals) in the central/eastern Pacific, strongly influencing global climate. While SST captures these events, it is noisier due to fast air–sea interactions; D20 varies more slowly through oceanic dynamics. We use annual mean SST and D20 data from EN4 (1950–2020) and ORAS5 (1958–2020), and historical SST from HadISST, ERSSTv5, and COBE. EOF analysis of D20 yields the first three modes, used to relate to POPL variability. Anomalies are detrended (linear for SST/D20, polynomial for POPL). Niño3.4 and PC1 of global D20 (30°S–30°N) are used to quantify potential predictability at various lead times.

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2.4 Detection of tipping point

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It is difficult to detect early warning signals of sudden changes or tipping point when the true process behind the data is unknown (e.g., Scheffer et al., 2009). There are several metric-based and model-based indicators for identifying critical transition. Nonparametric drift-diffusion-jump models help solve this by using a flexible approach that can approximate many different types of data patterns. Here we employ Nonparametric drift-diffusion-jump model (Carpenter & Brock, 2011; Dakos et al., 2012) on hPOPL data of India for identifying possible critical transition. In this model, drift measures the local rate of change, diffusion measures relatively small shocks that occur at each time step, jumps are large intermittent shocks. Total variance combines the contributions of diffusion and jumps. Increase in variance and jump intensity indicates a transition of the system to a different state (see Scheffer et al., 2009; Carpenter & Brock, 2011; Dakos et al., 2012). Furthermore, a sudden change in diffusion term may indicate that system has already crossed a critical point and entered to a new state (e.g., Dakos et al., 2012).

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3 Results

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3.1 Nonlinear trend and tipping point of POPL

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The POPL, both globally and over India, shows a rapid increase across the WBGT range of 15°–35°C (corresponding to a Humidex range of 25°–50°C) during 1950–2020 (Figure 1a,b,e,f). However, the threshold levels at which the maxima in POPL changes occur differ between the indices used. While the WBGT-based global POPL exhibits a maximum around 26°C (Figure 1a), the Humidex-based POPL reaches its maximum near 37°C (Figure 1b) in the recent decade. For India, the maxima in POPL occur at relatively higher thresholds compared to global average for both indices. Furthermore, the increase in POPL at lower thresholds is much steeper. Nevertheless, the changes at the extreme thresholds are of serious concern, as they have the potential to cause significant losses to life and productivity across regions or nations.

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The nonlinear growth of POPL from 1950 to 2020 for both Humidex > 45°C and WBGT > 33°C is illustrated in Figure 1 and summarized in Table 1. As POPL shows nonlinear growth in the last 71 years, a third-degree polynomial is used to fit the POPL and SST curve (shown by solid lines in Figure 1). Therefore, the difference between the polynomial curve and the POPL is considered a detrended annual anomaly of POPL. Having stratified by relative humidity, hPOPL is defined as POPL for relative humidity greater than 25%, while dry-POPL (dPOPL) is defined as POPL based on Humidex for relative humidity between 0–25%.

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A striking nonlinear increase in global hPOPL (Humidex > 45°C) by a factor of approximately 18, from about 37 billion person-hours in the first half of the 1950s to about 688 billion person-hours in the latter half of 2020s, with the most rapid increase occur-

Figure 1. Nonlinear trend and interannual variability of POPL. Variation of person-hour exposure with WBGT ($15^{\circ} - 35^{\circ}\text{C}$) during 1950-2020 for (a) global POPL and (e) Indian POPL. (b) and (f) are same as (a) and (e) respectively, but for Humidex for the range $25^{\circ} - 50^{\circ}\text{C}$. (c) Time series between 1950 and 2020 with humidex $> 45^{\circ}\text{C}$ for humid POPL (orange) and dry POPL (pink). POPL using WBGT $> 33^{\circ}\text{C}$ is in light blue color. Time series of global mean surface air temperature with its scale on the right (black line). Thick solid and dashed lines are 3rd order polynomial fit of annual POPL/temperature. (g) Same as (c) but for India. d) Global humid POPL with humidex $> 45^{\circ}\text{C}$ (green) and WBGT $> 33^{\circ}\text{C}$ (blue) by fixing the population at the 1950 level (dashed lines) and by normalizing with the working population (solid lines). h) same as d) but for India.

Table 1. Change in POPL in recent times compared to the 1950s. For the average of the first five years (1950-1954) and the last five years (2016-2020), the values of POPL and land surface air temperature are used.

	1950-1954 Avg.	2016-2020 Avg.	Factor of 1950-54
Global (WBGT > 33)			
POPL (total)	1.23×10^{10}	19.55×10^{10}	15.92
POPL (total) world population 1950	1.33×10^{10}	4.04×10^{10}	3.03
POPL (total) Normalized by total population	12.29	50.81	4.13
CRU surf Temp (°C)	12.85	14.13	
Global (Humidex > 45)			
dPOPL (RH 0-25)	3.90×10^9	32.98×10^9	8.45
hPOPL (RH > 25)	3.72×10^{10}	68.79×10^{10}	18.49
hPOPL (RH > 25) world population 1950	3.61×10^{10}	14.82×10^{10}	4.10
hPOPL (RH > 25) Normalized by total population	33.63	182.35	5.42
India (WBGT > 33)			
POPL (total)	0.49×10^{10}	9.32×10^{10}	19.06
POPL (total) world population 1950	0.56×10^{10}	2.04×10^{10}	3.64
POPL (total) Normalized by total population	34.99	127.72	3.65
CRU surf Temp (°C)	23.66	24.31	
India (Humidex > 45)			
dPOPL (RH 0-25)	2.18×10^9	16.88×10^9	7.74
hPOPL (RH > 25)	1.61×10^{10}	36.92×10^{10}	22.93
hPOPL (RH > 25) India population 1950	1.55×10^{10}	8.17×10^{10}	5.27
hPOPL (RH > 25) Normalized by total population	96.91	515.48	5.31

ring from the 1990s, is seen in Figure 1a and Table 1. The global dPOPL also increases nonlinearly by a factor of about 8.5, from about 3.9 billion person-hours in the 1950s to about 33 billion person-hours around 2020, with a rapid increase beginning around the 1990s. The gap between the dry and humid HOPL also increases rapidly, with the hPOPL being about 10 times larger than the dPOPL in the 1950s, increasing to about 21 times the dPOPL in the 2020s. Currently, India is the single largest contributor to global hPOPL (Figure 1b), accounting for about half of the worldwide hPOPL and growing from the 1950s to the 2020s by a staggering factor of about 23. Furthermore, the dPOPL also increased rapidly by a factor of about 8 during the period 1950 to 2022 (Table 1). The contribution of dPOPL to the total has decreased from about 11% in the 1950s to about 4% in the 2020s, making hPOPL the dominant contributor. However, globally, the contribution of dPOPL has decreased from about 8% in the 1950s to 4% in the 2020s. POLP, based on extreme Wet Bulb Globe Temperature ($WBGT > 33^{\circ}\text{C}$), also shows a similar trend. While globally, POPL has increased by approximately 16 times, the increase over India is about 19 times. Although there is no one-to-one correspondence between the thresholds of Humidex and WBGT, both indices show a similar orders of increase in POPL in the 2020s compared to the 1950s. It is important to note that the WBGT calculation takes into account sun-exposed conditions, wind, and radiant heat (see Data and Methods).

The amplitude of interannual variability superimposed on the nonlinear trend of hPOPL seems to have significantly increased in recent decades. To separate the interannual anomalies of POPL, the nonlinear trend is estimated by a third-degree polynomial (see methods) and shown by solid thick lines in Figure 1a,c. Further, the contribution from population growth to the nonlinear trend of global hPOPL is estimated from the time series of the same with population fixed at 1950 values (Figure 1b,d). Thus, the contribution to hPOPL (POPL) from climate change for $\text{Humidex} > 45^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($WBGT > 33^{\circ}\text{C}$) grows by a factor of about 4 (3) from the 1950s to the 2020s globally. A similar estimate for India's hPOPL (POPL) (Figure 1d) towards contribution from climate change for $\text{Humidex} > 45^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($WBGT > 33^{\circ}\text{C}$) also indicates growth by a factor of about 5 (4). An hPOPL/POPL weighted by the population at each location and normalized by the population of the region is also a natural way to isolate the climate change contribution to the nonlinear trend and growth (Figure 1b,d). It is noted that climate change induces growth of hPOPL for $\text{Humidex} > 45^{\circ}\text{C}$ by a factor of about 5 from the 1950s to the 2020s for both India and globally. Moreover, using $WBGT > 33^{\circ}$ the growth of POPL is about 4 times, both globally and over India. Clearly, the growth in hPOPL/POPL is influenced by both population growth and an increase in temperature. During the period from 1950 to 2020, the global population increased by a factor of 3.6, while that of India increased by a factor of 4.6 (Figure S2).

The rapid rise in hPOPL from the 1980s to 2020 (Figure 1) is closely associated with the accelerated global temperature increase (*WMO Global Annual to Decadal Climate Update*, 2024), driven by anthropogenic forcing and amplified by population growth. To test this, we use hPOPL from nine CMIP6 models (Table TS1) comparing (a) historical simulations (1950–2014, with anthropogenic forcings) and (b) pre-industrial control (piControl, natural forcings only). In piControl, ensemble-mean hPOPL increases by about 4 times (1950–1954 to 2010–2014) for $\text{Humidex} > 45^{\circ}\text{C}$, mainly from population growth (Figure S3, Table TS2). Historical runs underestimate observed growth, showing only a 4–6-fold increase. However, the historical–piControl difference, less sensitive to model biases, rises by about 14-fold globally and by about 9-fold for India, which are closer to observations (about 10-fold). While use of daily mean RH and T_{max} may overestimate Humidex, the actual underestimation of hPOPL by CMIP models is likely to be greater. These results strongly support that recent hPOPL increases are primarily anthropogenic.

Figure 2. Critical point in POPL in relation to an increase in warm pool SST and atmospheric moisture loading. a) Normalized tendency of annual POPL for dry (pink), humid (orange) humidex $> 45^{\circ}\text{C}$ and WBGT $> 33^{\circ}\text{C}$ (light blue). The time series of annual POPL are normalized by their mean over 71 years (1950-2020) before calculating the tendency. b) Warm-pool area-averaged (70° - 130°E , 20°S - 20°N) SST (black) and vertically integrated moisture (red; in mm), where dashed lines represent the linear trend. c) Historical records of warm pool SST based on four different data sets show that the mean SST has never crossed 28°C before the 1980s since the data began in 1857.

Figure 3. Metrics from Nonparametric drift-diffusion-jump model using hPOPL of India, based on WBGT (in red color) and Humidex (in blue color) , indicating critical transition. (A) The hPOPL time series for India. (B, C, D) total variance, diffusion and jump intensity, respectively with respect to time. (E,F,G) Same as B,C,D but as a function of hPOPL, where decline suggest a new state with low variability.

304 The rise in hPOPL (Figure 1a,c) reflects growing health costs (mortality, hospi-
 305 talization), economic losses (reduced productivity), and greater inequity, making it a use-
 306 ful indicator of potential socio-economic loss from climate change. There is growing recog-
 307 nition that many complex systems, including climate, possess critical thresholds, often
 308 referred to as tipping points, beyond which they undergo sudden and dramatic shifts from
 309 one state to another (e.g., Scheffer et al., 2009). The increase of hPOPL (Figure 1) is
 310 suggestive of crossing a tipping point or critical transition. Annual POPL tendencies (Fig-
 311 ure 2a) shifted from weakly positive in the 1950s to negative in the 1970s, turned pos-
 312 itive in the mid-1980s, and have since accelerated—most rapidly for hPOPL (Humidex)
 313 and total POPL (WBGT), indicating system instability. Neither temperature nor pop-
 314 ulation growth alone explains this surge. We identify hPOPL as a socio-economic tip-
 315 ping element of the Asian monsoon climate–population system, crossing a critical point
 316 in the mid-1980s. This coincides with: (1) global mean temperature accelerating (Intergovernmental
 317 Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2023; *WMO Global Annual to Decadal Climate Up-*
 318 *date*, 2024), (2) Asian monsoon Humidex exceeding 45° (Figure S4b), (3) warm pool SST
 319 surpassing the 28°C threshold for the first time in history (mid-1980s; Figure 2b,c), and
 320 (4) working-age population doubling since 1950 in India (Figure S2). These combined
 321 climatic and demographic thresholds triggered the rapid rise in hPOPL, exemplifying
 322 a climate–development feedback consistent with the Gaia hypothesis (J. E. Lovelock, 1983).

323 Figure 3 presents results from the nonparametric drift–diffusion–jump (DDJ) model
 324 applied to India’s hPOPL time series based on WBGT and Humidex. The panels show
 325 the evolution of total variance, jump intensity, and diffusion over time (Figure 3b–d) and
 326 as functions of hPOPL (Figure 3e–g). The results indicate that both total variance and
 327 jump intensity began to rise in the 1980s, while the diffusion term exhibited a sudden
 328 decrease around the same period. Notably, this coincides with a shift in vertically inte-
 329 grated humidity over the warm pool region (Figure 2c) and sea surface temperature (SST)
 330 crossing the 28°C threshold. In terms of hPOPL, the system appears to have become
 331 increasingly unstable around 50 billion person-hours (Figure 3F), and may have tran-
 332 sitioned to a different state at 85 billion person-hours based on WBGT and 340 billion
 333 person-hours based on Humidex (the peak). Afterward, the decrease in jump intensity
 334 and total variance indicates a transition to a different state in the present time with in-
 335 creasing hPOPL. We also note that the hPOPL derived from both indices exhibits re-
 336 markably similar behavior, including a distinct critical transition.

337 3.2 Disproportionate impact in tropical developing countries

338 Tropical regions, with their higher baseline temperatures, experience a much greater
 339 rise in atmospheric moisture for each 1°C warming than extra-tropics, due to the non-
 340 linear Clausius–Clapeyron relationship. Consequently, both the mean exposure to ex-
 341 treme heat and its increase since the 1950s are disproportionately larger in the tropics
 342 (Figure 4). From 1950 onward, annual hours exceeding Humidex $> 45^\circ$ or WBGT $>$
 343 33° have risen markedly across all regions, along with the spatial extent above fixed thresh-
 344 olds (e.g., >100 hours; Figure 4c,d). Countries with the greatest developmental needs,
 345 e.g., least-developed sub-Saharan nations, South and Southeast Asia (Iran, Iraq, India,
 346 Thailand, Myanmar, Vietnam), and parts of South America, suffer the highest poten-
 347 tial productivity loss, while developed northern countries face impacts an order of mag-
 348 nitude lower. POPL trends (Figure S5) show the top nine hPOPL countries are all tropi-
 349 cal; even China’s increase is limited to a small Southeast monsoon region. WBGT-based
 350 POPL shows similar patterns, reinforcing Humidex’s value as a communicable tropical
 351 heat indicator.

352 As evident in Figure 4, within the tropics, the zonal mean hPOPL as a function
 353 of latitude (Figure S7) indicates that the most affected countries are located centred around
 354 26°N and the three monsoon regions, namely, the African monsoon, the Asian monsoon,
 355 and the American monsoon. It is also notable that while the rural population started

Figure 4. Potential loss of hours across the globe due to extreme discomfort. The annual average potential hour loss during the 1950s (1950-1959) for a) WBGT > 33°C in hours/year, b) Humidex > 45°C in hours/year. Increase in annual potential hour loss between 1950 and 2020 based on linear trend analysis for c) WBGT > 33°C and d) Humidex > 45°C. Linear trends significant at above 99%, using the Mann-Kendall test, are stippled by black dots.

356 feeling notable hPOPL even in the 1950s and increased rapidly, the urban population
 357 started feeling it by the 1990s and grew more rapidly to catch up with rural hPOPL in
 358 the 2020s. India is a good example to illustrate the severity of the problem. On aver-
 359 age, the country lost about 12 population-normalized workdays a year (assuming an 8-
 360 hour workday) in the 1950s, increasing almost five-fold to about 65 workdays a year in
 361 the 2020s! Similarly, WBGT based hPOPL shows about three-fold increase loss of work-
 362 days. When the large human capital is considered, the ‘potential’ loss for the country
 363 is enormous (Figure 1c).

364 **3.3 The interannual variability and predictability of POPL**

365 The amplitude of interannual standard deviation of global and India hPOPL for
 366 WBGT > 33°C (Humidex > 45°C) are 11.2 and 3.5 (46.6 and 22.9) billion person-hours
 367 respectively. Skillful forewarning of the large interannual variability of hPOPL may be
 368 critical for building climate resilience for the loss of outdoor productivity in any coun-
 369 try. For this purpose, it is imperative to understand what drives the interannual vari-
 370 ability of hPOPL and its predictability at various lead time. An examination of the anoma-
 371 lies of interannual variability of hPOPL (Figure 1a,c) indicates that the global and In-
 372 dian hPOPL are nearly in phase ($r=0.94$ for Humidex > 45°C and $r=0.93$ for WBGT
 373 > 33°C) and that it is dominated by a quasi-four-year oscillation, potentially linked with
 374 the dominant interannual variability in the tropics, namely the El Niño and Southern
 375 Oscillation (ENSO).

376 To explore and quantify the potential connection between the ENSO and hPOPL/POPL,
 377 we define ENSO from the top three Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs) of the depth
 378 of the 20° isotherms in the ocean water over the Indo-Pacific tropical domain between
 379 1950 and 2020 (Figure S7). The three leading EOFs represent different aspects of the
 380 ENSO and correlate significantly with global as well as Indian hPOPL (Figure S7 d,e,f).
 381 While PC1 is significantly related to hPOPL, multiple regression analysis shows that the
 382 first three PCs collectively account for approximately 43% of the year-to-year variabil-
 383 ity in global hPOPL and 42% in Indian hPOPL. Moreover, the spatial pattern of cor-
 384 relation between the annual mean SST and hPOPL (Figure 5a,b and Figure S8a,b) is
 385 indicative of a strong association between hPOPL and interdecadal ENSO pattern (Zhang
 386 et al., 1997). It is noted that in recent years (1980-2020), this relationship is stronger
 387 (Figure 5a) compared to the last 71 years (i.e. 1950-2020; Figure S8), possibly due to
 388 better quality and a large number of observations in the post satellite era. Although, slightly
 389 weaker, a similar correlation pattern is evident when POPL based on WBGT > 33°C
 390 is used (Figure 7b, S8b). Furthermore, the interannual correlation between the two in-
 391 dices is 0.94 globally and 0.91 for India, indicating a strong consistency between the two
 392 heat metrics employed in this study.

393 To explore the potential predictability of hPOPL/POPL from an index of ENSO,
 394 we examined lead-lag correlations of hPOPL/POPL anomalies with the 3-month run-
 395 ning mean of Niño3.4 SST anomaly and PC1 of D20 (Figure 5c, Figure S8 c). The PC1
 396 of D20 also represents the canonical ENSO and is not directly affected by fast-evolving
 397 atmospheric noise, making it potentially a better predictor. The fact that ENSO leads
 398 global (India) hPOPL by 1 month with a correlation skill of 0.75 (0.7). Furthermore, the
 399 skill is higher when using the PC1 of D20 compared to the Niño3.4 index; however, it
 400 is notable that total POPL based on WBGT is less predictable. In the case of India, hPOPL/POPL
 401 primarily occurs during the boreal summer months (i.e., June to September) and is ac-
 402 tually predictable with a lead time of about 6 months, with a correlation skill of 0.7. More-
 403 over, since ENSO is now predictable more than a year in advance (Wang et al., 2023),
 404 our findings suggest that useful prediction of global or India hPOPL one year in advance
 405 is possible.

Figure 5. Predictability of the year-to-year variation of POPL in the recent past 41 years (1980-2020). a) Anomaly correlation between hPOPL (humidex > 45°C) in India and global sea surface temperature, indicating significant predictability linked to ENSO. b) Same as a), but using hPOPL with WBGT > 33°C. Correlations significant at the 5% level are stippled with black dots. c) Correlation between ENSO indices (Niño3.4 and PC1 of the 20°C isotherm depth (i.e. D20) of the ocean) and hPOPL at various lead (up to 7) and lag (up to 5) months. Thick (thin) solid and dashed lines represent India’s (global) hPOPL predictability. Here, a 3-month running average of the Niño3.4 index and D20 are correlated with annual hPOPL (with Humidex > 45°C/WBGT > 33°C) to demonstrate useful predictability of hPOPL with the lead time. Lead-0 indicates the previous year’s October-to-December averaged Niño3.4/PC1 of D20.

4 Discussions and Conclusions

The climate and environment, comprising living and non-living components, are two interacting parts of the Earth System, maintaining a stable equilibrium oscillating between glacial and interglacial periods over the past million years (Barbante et al., 2010), much like the self-regulating planet envisioned in the Gaia hypothesis (Lovelok & Margulis, 1974; J. E. Lovelock, 1983; J. Lovelock, 2016). In the last 200 years, however, industrialization has degraded the environment so severely that seven of eight safe and just Earth System boundaries have crossed tipping points (Steffen et al., 2018; Rockström et al., 2023; Steffen et al., 2015), raising the risk of a transition to a hothouse climate (Scotese, 2015; Lenart, 2010; Schröder & Storm, 2020). With emissions rising alongside GDP, it remains uncertain whether internal Earth System feedbacks can avert this shift. From 2000–2019, an estimated 0.5 million people died annually from heat stress (Zhao et al., 2021), and evidence shows health risks are worsening regardless of the metric used (Alahmad et al., 2023; La, 2024).

The sharp rise in hPOPL over the past three decades coincides with global mean temperature surpassing 1°C above pre-industrial levels, pushing tropical warm pool temperatures beyond 28°C in the mid-1980s. This triggered rapid increases in evaporation and atmospheric moisture, breaching the hPOPL critical point. Consequently, the summer monsoon climatology of daily maximum Humidex in northwest India (e.g., New Delhi) neared the critical 45°C , with almost every rain-free day exceeding this threshold (Figure S4). As such extremes are tied to ‘break monsoon’ days, further increases may mainly result from extending the warm rainy season, suggesting slower hPOPL growth in the next decade.

The possibility of critical transition is tested using nonparametric drift-diffusion-jump model. The increase in total variance and jump intensity (or frequency of sudden changes) and decrease in diffusion since 1980s indicates beginning of critical transition of hPOPL (Figure 3). Furthermore, a peak or maxima and down slope in total variance and jump intensity in the recent past years indicate its transition to a relatively stable new state with less inter-annual variability.

Since Gilbert Walker’s discovery of the ENSO–ISMR link (Walker, 1924), ENSO has been recognized as a dominant driver of interannual variability of ISMR and monsoon-region temperatures (Rasmusson & Carpenter, 1982, 1983; Webster et al., 1998). Therefore, it is not surprising that ENSO is associated with India hPOPL. Given India’s dominant contribution to global hPOPL and their strong correlation ($r=0.94$), ENSO largely modulates global hPOPL via its impact on India. ENSO may also influence global hPOPL directly by modulating annual global surface temperature (AGST), as El Niño events strongly relate to AGST, though not vice versa (Privalsky & Yushkov, 2015; Banholzer & Donner, 2014; Tsonis et al., 2005). Beyond productivity loss, the rising exposure of workers to critical heat stress is a major health risk, underscoring the need for robust adaptation, preparedness, and skilful hPOPL prediction to guide policy.

Although developed countries of the global North are chiefly responsible for climate change, its humid heat stress impacts disproportionately affect the developing countries of the global South, constraining their development by rapidly reducing potential productive hours. Our finding of a sharp rise in potential socio-economic loss, possibly crossing a critical threshold, may push policymakers toward sustainable development pathways such as the Degrowth model (Hickel et al., 2021, 2022; Cosme et al., 2017). Gains from a growing workforce are outweighed by faster losses in productive hours from extreme events. Urgent recognition and climate action are essential to keep Earth habitable and avoid a hothouse future.

Open Research Section

The hourly 2m air temperature (T_a) and dew point temperature (T_d) from European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalysis version 5 (ERA5) (Hersbach et al., 2020) for 1940-2020 with $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ horizontal resolution is used. Annual mean SST and D20 depth data from EN4 analysis (Good et al., 2013) for 1950-2020 and from Ocean Reanalysis System 5 (ORAS5) of ECMWF (Copernicus Climate Change Service, Climate Data Store, 2021) for 1958 to 2020 are used. SST data from HadISST v1.1 (Rayner et al., 2003) for 1870 to 2020, ERSST v5 (Huang et al., 2017) for 1854 to 2020, and COBE (Ishii et al., 2005) for 1891 to 2020 are also used to show historical changes in warm pool temperature. Gridded specific humidity from the surface to 200 hPa level is taken from ERA-5 reanalysis for 1950-2020. Daily relative humidity and daily maximum temperature (T_{max}) from nine CMIP6 models (Table 2) for historical and piControl simulations (1950-2014) are used to estimate the change in POPL due to anthropogenic influences. The annual demographic data with $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ resolution for 1950-2020 is used from (Chambers, 2020). This data contains age-wise number of population (0 to 65 years with intervals of 5 years, i.e. 0, 5, 10, ..., 65). In addition to this, gridded ($0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$) total, urban and rural population data for 1950-2020 is also used (*ISIMIP3a population input data*, 2024) to quantify POPL exposure levels in the rural and urban areas. The figures are created using GrADS (<http://opengrads.org/>) and NCL (<http://dx.doi.org/10.5065/D6WD3XH5>) software.

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